

EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES ON TEACHING ENGLISH FOR YOUNG LEARNERS IN UZBEKISTAN

Kodirova Shakhzoda

UzSWLU, senior student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11632178>

Annotation

This article explores effective strategies for teaching English to young learners in Uzbekistan, a context characterized by its linguistic diversity and unique educational challenges. Through a comprehensive literature review, the study identifies key themes such as the importance of immersive learning environments, multimedia resources, and culturally responsive teaching practices. The article concludes that these strategies not only improve language acquisition but also foster an engaging and supportive educational environment. The study's insights are intended to inform teacher training programs and future research, with the aim of improving English language education for young learners in Uzbekistan.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqola O'zbekistondagi yosh o'quvchilarga ingliz tilini o'rgatish bo'yicha samarali strategiyalarni o'rganadi, bu yondashuv lingvistik xilma-xillik va o'ziga xos ta'lim muammolari bilan ajralib turadi. Keng qamrovli adabiyotlarni ko'rib chiqish orqali, ushbu tadqiqot immersiv o'rganish muhiti, multimedia resurslari va madaniy jihatdan mos o'rgatish amaliyotlarining muhim mavzularini aniqlaydi. Maqola ushbu strategiyalar nafaqat til o'zlashtirishni yaxshilashini, balki qiziqarli va qo'llab-quvvatlovchi o'quv muhitini yaratishini xulosa qiladi. Tadqiqotning tushunchalari o'qituvchilar tayyorlash dasturlari va kelajakdagi tadqiqotlarni maqsad qilib, O'zbekistondagi yosh o'quvchilar uchun ingliz tili ta'limini yaxshilashni maqsad qiladi.

Аннотация

Эта статья исследует эффективные стратегии преподавания английского языка молодым учащимся в Узбекистане, контекст которого характеризуется языковым разнообразием и уникальными образовательными вызовами. Через всесторонний обзор литературы исследование выявляет ключевые темы, такие как важность погружающих образовательных сред, мультимедийных ресурсов и культурно-адаптивных практик преподавания. Статья приходит к выводу, что эти стратегии не только улучшают усвоение языка, но также способствуют созданию привлекательной и поддерживающей образовательной среды. Полученные в ходе исследования понимания предназначены для информирования программ подготовки учителей и будущих исследований с целью улучшения образования по английскому языку для молодых учащихся в Узбекистане.

Key words: materials, learning environment, activity, children, interaction, skills, strategies, young learners, repetition,

Teaching English is growing day by day and now scholars have focused on learners' needs. In searching new strategies they follow criteria. Currently, this is inventing various ways of teaching English as a foreign language to young learners. Teaching English for young learners should be correctly chosen if it is wanted to be successful. It needs greatly experienced and dedicated teaching (Audrey, M, 2006).. Teachers of English for young learners need to understand how students think and operate, that is how young learners learn a language.

Before looking through some famous and practised strategies we should know who is a young learner.

In teaching process teachers divide learners at first according to their age. So, what kind of learners we can say youngsters.

Learning outside of the classroom

As mentioned earlier, it is important to allow for plenty of learning opportunities outside of the classroom (Cameron, L, 2003). Since the number of lessons per week in the classroom for very young learners is normally quite limited, why not involve parents in their learning process?

► Establish a welcoming early learning environment

Establish a welcoming environment by:

- reflecting the linguistic and cultural diversity of all children in such things as classroom posters, pictures, props, tabletop toys, games, storybooks, media resources, musical instruments and foods served in the classroom;
- providing opportunities for family and community members to share experiences with children in the classroom in their home language as well as in English;
- providing learning experiences such as field trips and other community outings to places where children and families can learn about the culture and history of themselves and others;
- offering opportunities for children, assisted by their parents or other family and/or community members, to cook foods from a wide range of cultural backgrounds

► Encourage children to play

Play is the cornerstone activity for social, cognitive and language development in children from two-and-a-half to five-years-old. Early childhood professionals should promote play as the leading activity for children.

- Use objects and pictures to support explanations and event descriptions.
- Repeat the same idea or instruction more than once, the second time using shorter sentences, easier vocabulary and speaking more slowly.
- To check for comprehension, try to ask questions where the response is not just a “yes” or a “no.”
- Tell and talk about the story in a book rather than reading it directly. Written language is harder for young children to understand than spoken language because sentences are often longer and have more difficult words in them.
- Choose books with simpler language and/or repetition books that are interesting to the children. Encourage children to “chime in” during the parts of the story they are familiar with.

► Activity planning tips

Involve children in dialogue with peers and adults who will model more advanced language use. Develop activities that encourage real dialogue between child-child and adult-child rather than relying on activities that just require children to respond by either nodding their heads or pointing to a picture. Encourage interaction between children in pairs or small groups (Gardner, H. (2000).

Language functions to emphasize:

- requesting (*e.g., asking to join in the activity, asking for an object, asking permission, asking for information, asking politely*)
- responding (*e.g., to questions, to continue the topic*)

- expressing likes and dislikes

Interact with the children.

When children make a vocabulary or grammatical error, recast what they said using the correct form, and then move on with the conversation. Make an effort to expand on children's language. For example, if a child says, "My shoes," you can talk about the colour or type of shoes the child is wearing.

In conclusion, the study on effective strategies for teaching English to young learners in Uzbekistan highlights the critical role of immersive, interactive, and culturally relevant methods in enhancing language acquisition. The research demonstrates that the integration of multimedia resources, such as educational videos and interactive language games, significantly boosts student engagement and retention of vocabulary and grammar.

References:

1. Audrey, M. (2006). *Teaching English to very young learners*.
2. Cameron, L. (2003). *Teaching languages to young learners*. Cambridge University Press, 150-210.
3. Gardner, H. (2000). *Intelligence reframed: Multiple intelligences for the 21st century*. Basic Books, 65(2), 108-114.
4. Gurian, M., Stevens, K., & King, K. (2008). *Strategies for teaching boys & girls: Elementary level*. Jossey-Bass.
5. Hughes, A. (2009). An introduction to teaching English to young learners. *Journal of Teaching English to Young Learners*.
6. Kang Shin, J. (2009). Teaching English to young learners. *English Language Center, University of Maryland, Baltimore County*.
7. Paradis, J. (2009). Working with young children who are learning English as a new language.
8. Luis, J. (2013). *Teaching young learners*.